

Composites, Present and Future in Aeritalia

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ABSTRACT

A synthesis of the status of composites in Aeritalia is given with respect to its major production program 767 and future programs. Steps to be followed to grow from the actual semiartigianal status to a high degree of automation are described.

All significant steps, from design to fabrication and control are examined in order to rationalize them and modify them to implement a high degree of automation which is considered the only answer to the increasing demand of composite structures. A flow diagram of all the activities involved in the industrialization of composites will be given where all the connections are clearly indicated.

Four levels of activity in the whole process of industrialization are separated and goals for each level defined.

